

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF SPEECH EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the subject of preschool education "Speech Development Methodology", as well as the purpose, objectives, object, subject, main sources of the subject, the relationship of the subject with other disciplines, the principles of speech development methodology for the development of oral speech in preschool children, the requirements, methods, forms, problems of speech development, effective communication of one's thoughts, clear, logical, clear, fluent speech, ways to correctly formulate speech in the upbringing of a harmonious generation and the effectiveness of work, and the issues of teaching children to communicate with other people. Also, this textbook covers the basics of mastering the logical and emotional-figurative expression of reading and speech, the ability to analyze and perform a work of art, and the skills of children to establish speech activity.

This article can be used by undergraduate students of higher education, educators, young teachers who want to develop their professional competence, graduate students, researchers, and those interested in the field of pedagogy.

KEYWORDS: Professional knowledge, skills, consistent development of qualifications, professional competence qualities, innovative ideas, innovative ideas, Association, continuous, system, core, element, mature, professional, creative.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim yo'nalishining "Nutq o'stirish metodikasi" fani, hamda o'quv predmetining maqsadi, vazifalari, ob'yekti, predmeti, asosiy manbalari, fanning boshqa fanlar bilan aloqasi, nutq o'stirish metodikasining maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda og'zaki nutqni rivojlantirish tamoyillari, unga qo'yilgan talablar, usullari, shakllari, nutqni rivojlantirish muammolari, o'z fikrini ta'sirchan yetkazish, tushunarli, mantiqiy, aniq, ravon nutqqa ega bo'lishi, barkamol avlod tarbiyasida nutqni to'g'ri shakllantirish yo'llari va ish samaradorligi, boshqa kishilar bilan muloqot qila olishga o'rgatish masalalari haqida so'z boradi.

Shuningdek, ushbu darslikda o'qish va nutqning mantiqiy va xis-xayajonli-obrazli ifoda-sini o'zlashtirishlari, badiiy asarni taxlil qilish va uni ijro eta olishni bilish, bolalarga nutq faoliyatini yo'lga qo'yish malakalariga ega bo'lishi asoslari yoritilgan.

Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'limning bakalvriat bosqichi talabalari, pedagoglar, kasbiy kom-petentligini rivojlantirish istagida bo'lgan yosh o'qituvchilar, magistrantlar, ilmiy izlanuvchilar va pedagogika sohasiga qiziquvchilar foydalanishlari mumkin.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В Данной Статье Рассматривается Предмет «Методика Развития Речи» В Дошкольном Образовании, А Также Цель, Задачи, Объект, Предмет, Основные Источники Предмета, Связь Предмета С Другими Дисциплинами, Принципы Методики Развития Речи Для Развития Устной Речи У Детей Дошкольного Возраста, Требования, Методы, Формы, Проблемы Развития Речи, Эффективное Сообщение Своих Мыслей, Ясная, Логичная, Четкая, Плавная Речь, Способы Правильного Формирования Речи В Воспитании Гармоничного Поколения, Эффективность Работы, Вопросы Обучения Детей Общению С Другими Людьми.

В Учебнике Также Рассматриваются Основы Овладения Логической И Эмоционально-Образной Выразительностью Чтения И Речи, Умения Анализировать И Воспроизводить Художественное Произведение, Умения Детей Организовывать Речевую Деятельность.

Статья Может Быть Полезна Студентам Высших Учебных Заведений, Преподавателям, Молодым Учителям, Желаящим Повысить Свою Профессиональную Компетентность, Аспирантам, Научным Сотрудникам, А Также Всем, Кто Интересуется Педагогикой.

TAYANCH SO‘ZLAR:

sohaviy bilim, ko'nikma, malakalarini izchil rivojlantirish, kasbiy kompetentlik sifatlarini innovatik g'oyalami, innovatik g'oyalami, Assotsiatsiyasi, uzluksiz,tizim,yadro,element,etuk,kasbiy,ijodiy.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА:

Последовательное развитие профессиональных знаний, навыков, квалификаций, инновационных идей, Ассоциация профессиональных компетентностных качеств, непрерывный, системный, основной, элемент, зрелый, профессиональный, творческий.

Bugungi kunda O'zbekiston Respublikasida ta'lim tizimida ijtimoiy hayotning barcha sohalarida bo'lgani kabi keng ko'lami islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Islohotlarning ko'lami shu darajadaki, unda uzluksiz ta'lim tizimini barcha bosqichlari – maktabgacha ta'limdan tortib toki kadrlarni qayta tayyorlash, ularning malakasini oshirish bosqichi, qolaversa, ta'lim tizimini boshqarish bo'g'inigacha bo'lgan jarayonlar qamrab olingan. Zero, mazkur bosqichlarning har

biri yaxlit tizim bo'lgan ta'lim sohasining muhim tarkibiy elementlari bo'lib, ular bir-birlarini taqozo etadi, o'zaro aloqadorlik va bog'liqlikda rivojlanadi.

Mavjud sharoitda, ta'limiy islohotlar doirasida yosh avlodga ta'lim-tarbiya berish jarayonining asosiy ishtirokchisi bo'lgan o'qituvchi, pedagoglarni tayyorlash, ularni kasbiy shakllantirish, sohaviy bilim, ko'nikma, malakalarini izchil rivojlantirish, kasbiy kompetentlik sifatlarini mustahkamlashga alohida e'tibor qaratilayotganligi oliy ta'lim muassasalarida o'qitish sifatini yaxshilash, samaradorligini oshirish barcha davrlarda bo'lgani kabi dolzarb muammo ekanligini tasdiqlaydi. Binobarin, o'qituvchi, pedagoglarning bilim darajasi, kasbiy tajribasi, pedagogik kompetentligi, ilg'or ish uslublari, kasbiy faoliyatiga bo'lgan zamonaviy yondashuvlari yosh avlodga ta'lim berish, uni barkamol shaxs etib tarbiyalashga qo'yilayotgan ijtimoiy talablarni to'g'ri anglash, zimmalariga yuklatilgan vazifani mavjud talablardan kelib chiqqan holda oqilona tashkil etish uchun muhim "yadro" bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Respublikamizda uzluksiz ta'lim tizimining barcha bosqichlariga, jumladan uning maktabgacha ta'lim bosqichiga e'tibor ortib borishi bilan bir qatorda maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlariga jalb etish (Qamrab olish) ulushi kamayib borishi bu borada maqsadli tadqiqotlar olib borish, mamlakatimiz ilmiy-texnikaviy dasturi, ustuvor tadqiqotlarga yo'nalishlarining bir qismi sifatida qaralishi lozim. Zero, ta'kidlab o'tganimizdek, uzluksiz ta'lim bosqichlarining nechog'lik samarali ishlashi ma'lum darajada maktabgacha ta'lim sifatiga bog'liq: bu davrda bolaning dunyoqarashi, tasavvurlari shakllanib bo'ladi. Unga to'g'ri mazmun va yo'nalish berish pedagogika fani, ta'lim amaliyotining dolzarb muammosidir. Bola nutqini rivojlantirish, eng avvalo, til qobi-lyatini shakllantirishni talab qiluvchi muloqot shakllarini rivojlantiruvchi demakdir Ilmiy tadqiqotlar va yo'nalishlar tahlili maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqining turli tomonlarini rivojlantirish xususiyatlari hamda ularning ilmiy adabiyotda o'rganilganlik darajasini aniqlash imkonini beradi. Zamonaviy o'quv adabiyotlarining yangi avlodini yaratish murakkab, mas'uliyatli jarayon bo'lib, unda pedagogika sohasida ro'y berayotgan o'zgarishlar, komil inson, malakali mutaxassisni tayyorlash borasidagi ijtimoiy ehtiyoj hamda shaxs kamolotida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadigan ustuvor tamoyillarni inobatga olish zarur. Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarining bakalavriat yo'nalishi talabalari uchun mo'ljallangan mazkur maqolada yoritilgan nutq o'stirish metodikasining o'qitishga qo'yilayotgan talablar imkon qadar to'la qamrab olishga qaratilgan.

Bolalarni nutqini o'stirish fanining maqsad va vazifalarida belgilanishicha Maktabgacha ta'lim sog'lom, har tomonlama yetuk bolalarni tarbiyalash uchun zarur tashkiliy, uslubiy, psixologik, pedagogik shart-sharoit yaratadi, bolalarni maktabda muntazam ravishda ta'lim olishga tayyorlashda ota-onalarga yordam

beradi. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlaridagi ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida ilg'or pedagogik va axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish, tashkilotlarni zamonaviy bilimlarga ega tarbiyachilar bilan to'ldirish hamda ularda kasbiy malaka, faoliyatga nisbatan ijodiy yondashuv hissini qaror toptirish, uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida olib borilayotgan islohotlarning muhim yo'nalishlaridan biri ekanligi alohida e'tirof etilgan. Kadrlar tayyorlash milliy dasturida qayd etilganidek, maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirish bo'yicha malakali tarbiyachi va pedagog kadrlar bugungi kunda uzluksiz innovatsion izlanishda bo'lishni, fikrlashi, shuningdek, MTTlarda ham innovativ g'oyalarni shakllantirish asosida faoliyat ko'rsatishlari lozim.

Bolalar nutqini o'stirish metodikasi Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutqni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan pedagogik faoliyat qonuniyatlarini o'rganuvchi fandır.

Metodikaning asosiy vazifasi – ilmiy-pedagogika sohasida nutqni rivojlantirishning eng samarali vositalari, metodlari va usullarini ishlab chiqish hamda bolalarda zarur nutqiy ko'nikmalarni muvaffaqiyatli ravishda rivojlantirishlari uchun bolalar bog'chalari tarbiyachilarini ular bilan qurollantirishdan iboratdir. Bolalarni nutqini o'stirish metodikasining asosiy mazmuni – bolalarda og'zaki nutqni, uning atrofdagilar bilan nutqiy muloqot ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishdir. Nutqni rivojlantirish metodikasi quyi-dagi asosiy savollarga javob topish imkonini beradi: nimani o'qitish (bolalarda qanday nutqiy ko'nikmani tarbiyalash), qanday o'qitish (bolalar nutqini shakllantirishda qanday sharoitlarda qaysi metod va usullardan foydalanish lozim), nega aynan shu yo'lda o'qitish zarur (nutqni rivojlantirishning taklif etilayotgan usullari nazariya va amaliyotning qaysi ma'lumotlariga asoslanmoqda).

Bolalar nutqini o'stirish nazariyasida bolalarga ona tilini o'rgatishning ob'ektiv xususiyatlari aks ettirilgan, nutqni rivojlantirish metodikasi sohasida O'zbekiston Respublikasida va xorijda yaratilgan va hozirda mavjud bo'lgan barcha ijobiy natijalar umumlashtirilgan.

Bolalar nutqini o'stirish nazariyasi metodik amaliyot bilan birga-likda rivojlanmoqda. Ayrim metodik qoidalarning yashovchanligi amaliyotda tekshirib ko'rilmoqda, amaliyotning o'zi fan oldiga hali o'z yechimini topmagan muhim masalalarni qo'yimoqda.

Metodik nazariyani bilmaydigan tarbiyachi faqat o'z farazlaridan kelib chiqib yoki boshqalarning tajribalaridan nusxa ko'chirgan holda bolalarni ko'r-ko'rona tarbiyalaydilar. U ko'p narsani nazardan qochiradi, chunki rang-barang metodlar va usullarni bilmaydi.

Bolalar nutqini o'stirish metodikasi maktabgacha ta'limdagi boshqa xususiy metodikalar bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'ladi, chunki nutq-bola shaxsini to'la-to'kis, rivojlantirishning eng muhim vositalaridan biridir. Atrofdagilarni tushunish va

bolaning o‘z faol nutqi har qanday pedagogik jarayonda zarur. Nutq bolaning butun faoliyatida unga yo‘ldosh bo‘ladi.

Pedagog kadrlarning uzluksiz ta‘lim olishini tashkil etish muam-molari bir qator xalqaro tashkilotlarda, jumladan, Jahon ta‘limini reja-lashtirish instituti (Parij), innovatik g‘oyalarni ta‘lim bo‘yicha instituti (Gamburg), Oliy ta‘limning Yevropa Markazi (Buxarest), Yevropa Mua‘llimlar ta‘limi Assotsiatsiyasi (ATEE) va boshqa qator ilmiy tashkilot-larda tadqiq etilmoqda.

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Bola nutqini rivojlantirish, eng avvalo, til qobiliyatini shakllanti-rishni talab qiluvchi muloqot shakllarini rivojlantiruvchi demakdir Ilmiy tadqiqotlar va yo‘nalishlar tahlili maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqi-ning turli tomonlarini rivojlantirish xususiyatlari hamda ularning ilmiy adabiyotda o‘rganilganlik darajasini aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Nowadays as in all spheres of social life, large-scale reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, are carried out in the educational system. The scope of reforms is such that it covers all stages of the system of continuing education – from preschool education to the retraining of personnel, the stage of their professional development, and, moreover, the management unit of the educational system. After all, each of these stages are important structural elements of the educational sphere, which is a holistic system, they dictate each other, develop in interrelationship and dependence.

In the current conditions, the fact that special attention is paid to the training of teachers, educators, their professional formation, consistent development of field knowledge, skills, qualifications, strengthening the qualities of professional competence, which are the main participants in the educational and educational process for the younger generation within the framework of educational reforms, confirms that improving the quality of training in higher educational institutions, improving Consequently, the level of knowledge, professional experience,

pedagogical competence, advanced working methods, modern approaches to professional activities of teachers, educators serve as an important “core” for teaching the younger generation, for the correct understanding of the social requirements for educating it as a competent person, for the rational organization of the task assigned to them based on existing requirements.

In addition to the increased attention to all stages of the continuing education system in our republic, its preschool education stage, the decrease in the share of involvement(coverage) of preschool children in preschool educational organizations should be considered as part of the scientific and technical program of our country, Priority Research in this regard. After all, as we noted, to some extent, the effective functioning of the stages of continuing education depends on the quality of preschool education: during this period, the worldview, imagination of the child can be formed. Giving it the right content and direction is an urgent problem of pedagogical science, educational practice. The development of Child speech means, first of all, the development of forms of communication that require the formation of a language Bowl-lyate analysis of scientific research and directions makes it possible to determine the features of the development of various aspects of speech of preschool children, as well as the degree of their study in the scientific literature. The creation of a new generation of modern educational literature is a complex, responsible process, in which it is necessary to take into account the changes that are taking place in the field of pedagogy, the social need for the training of a perfect person, a qualified specialist, as well as the priority principles that are important in the maturation of the individual. The teaching requirements of the speech culture methodology, which are covered in this article, aimed at students of the undergraduate direction of pedagogical higher education institutions, are aimed at covering as fully as possible.

As defined in the goals and objectives of the science of raising children's speech, preschool education creates the necessary organizational, methodological, psychological, pedagogical conditions for the upbringing of healthy, comprehensively mature children, helps parents in preparing children for regular education at school. It is especially noted that the use of advanced pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process in preschool educational organizations, filling organizations with educators with modern knowledge and finding a sense of professional competence, creative approach to activities in them, is one of the important areas of reforming carried out in the system of continuing education. As noted in the national program of Personnel Training, qualified educational and pedagogical personnel for improving the preschool education

system should operate on the basis of the formation of an innovative idea in continuous innovative research, thinking, as well as in MTTTS today.

The methodology for growing children's speech is aimed at the development of speech in preschool children-a science that studies the laws of pedagogical activity.

The main task of the methodology is to develop the most effective means, methods and methods of speech development in the field of scientific and pedagogical activity, and to arm kindergarten educators with them so that they can successfully develop the necessary speech skills in children. The main content of the methodology for growing children's speech is the formation of oral speech in children, the skills of speech communication with those around him. The methodology for the development of speech makes it possible to find answers to the main questions at the bottom: what to teach (what speech skills to educate children), what to teach (under what conditions to use which methods and methods in the formation of children's speech), why it is necessary to teach exactly on this path (what data of theory and

In the theory of growing children's speech, the objective features of duck-tooth native to children are reflected, in the field of speech development meto-Dicas created in the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad, and all the currently available positive results are summarized.

The theory of growing children's speech is developing along with methodological practice. The viability of certain methodological rules is being investigated in the ama-liyot, the practice itself puts before Science important issues that have not yet found a solution.

An educator who does not know methodical theory will blindly raise children only based on their own hypotheses or copying from the experiences of others. He avoids considering a lot, because he does not know colorful methods and methods.

The methodology for growing children's speech will be inextricably linked with other private methodologies in preschool education, since speech is one of the most important means of full-fledged, development of the child's personality. Understanding everyone around and the child's own active speech is necessary in any pedagogical process. Speech becomes a companion for the child in his entire career.

The organization of continuing education of pedagogical personnel muam-molar is being researched in a number of international organizations, including the Institute for the planning of World Education (Paris), the Institute for education of the innovative ideal (Hamburg), the European Center for Higher Education

(Bucharest), the European Association for Education of teachers (ATEE) and a number of scientific organizations.

In addition to the increased attention to all stages of the continuing education system in our republic, its preschool education stage, the decrease in the share of involvement of preschool children in preschool educational organizations should be considered as part of the scientific and technical program of our country, Priority Research in this regard. After all, as we noted, to some extent, the effective functioning of the stages of continuing education depends on the quality of preschool education: during this period, the worldview, imagination of the child can be formed. Giving it the right content and direction is an urgent problem of pedagogical science, educational practice.

The development of Child speech means, above all, the development of forms of communication that require the formation of language skills-analysis of scientific research and directions makes it possible to determine the features of the development of various aspects of speech of preschool children, as well as the degree of their study in the scientific literature.

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